

Project number: 730879

Project acronym: INFRAFRONTIER2020

Project title: Development of mouse mutant resources for functional analyses of human diseases - Enhancing the translation of research into innovation

D2.2 Reports on 2 INFRAFRONTIER Advanced Training Schools

Written by:

Elodie Bedu, CERBM-GIE (Phenomin-ICS)

Compiled by:

Asrar Ali Khan, INFRAFRONTIER GmbH

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730879.

Table of Contents

- 1. Background: Inception and main goals of the training schools 1**
- 2. School schedule and layout..... 1**
- 3. Information about the schools 3**
 - Programmes & special topics 3
 - Participants 4
- 4. Outcomes and feedback..... 6**
- 5. Future plans 7**
- 6. Annexes: 8**

1. Background: Inception and main goals of the training schools

The mouse is the model organism of choice to understand the underlying mechanisms of pathogenesis, for new target identification and preclinical applications. The ICS (Institut Clinique de la Souris, Strasbourg, France) is specialized in the generation of genetically modified mice and rats, and their clinical characterization *in vivo* (anatomical, physiological and behavioural phenotype) and ensures the development of new tools in these fields through the French PHENOMIN Infrastructure. In 2015, PHENOMIN organized the first edition of the **European Advanced School in mouse phenogenomics - Good practices in the use of mouse models for scientific and biomedical research purposes**. The school covers one of the main PHENOMIN's mission, i.e to support the organisation of the French scientific community by disseminating knowledge and standard processes by state-of-the-art training courses.

The principal aims trainings schools are:

- i) Accelerate the dissemination of conceptual scientific advances and the transfer of innovative and standardized methods and techniques in rodent functional genomics
- ii) Help to structure the scientific community and to promote interactions between specialists in phenogenomics and animal experimentation in different scientific themes and applications, in order to strengthen the relationship between doctoral training and scientific research
- iii) Address the issue of continuing professional education consistent with the new European directive requirements about regulatory training and lab animal experiments.

To ensure the highest standards in mouse phenogenomics, INFRAFRONTIER2020 offered an outstanding and innovative training program focussing on best practices in the use of the mouse model for biomedical research. This was built on the extensive expertise of the INFRAFRONTIER network in mouse cryopreservation and phenotyping courses, and the concept of the pilot phenogenomics course that was pioneered by the French PHENOMIN partner.

To ensure the highest standards in mouse phenogenomics, INFRAFRONTIER2020 offered an outstanding and innovative training program focusing on best practices in the use of the mouse model for biomedical research. It was built on the extensive expertise of the INFRAFRONTIER network in mouse cryopreservation and phenotyping courses, and the concept of the pilot phenogenomics course that was pioneered by the French PHENOMIN partner.

2. School schedule and layout

The Advanced PHENOMIN School was organised every 2 years at Château du Liebfrauenberg in Alsace, France – a quiet and pleasant environment perfectly adapted to gather a group that needs to be structured around a seminar and work room for 5 days.

The 5 days training program covered state-of-the-art approaches in diverse topics ranging from mouse genetics, mutagenesis and colony management to the development of mouse models of human diseases and phenotyping strategies including statistical analyses. A focus was on animal sciences, ethics and animal welfare and guidelines for reporting animal experiments. Furthermore, participants were trained in accessing existing European and international mouse resources and data that are available to the scientific community. The course and training format involved formal presentations by experts from among the INFRAFRONTIER network and further external experts, interactive discussions on selected scientific and technical issues as well as poster sessions. Priority was given to European participants but the course was also opened to other interested applicants. The course was jointly run with PHENOMIN every other year with up to 40 participants.

The main topics of the extensive programme covered the following fields of mouse functional genomics.

AXIS 1: Genetics of mice and other rodent models - historical perspective and new developments in mouse lines. Mutagenesis - from point mutation to major revisions, good practice, current and future prospects.

AXIS 2: Zootechnics - increasingly safe breeding, controlled breeding, health standards and impact on functional studies, management of colonies of genetically modified mice, background and genetic drift. Ethics and Animal Welfare - good practices for good results.

AXIS 3: Functional exploration of mouse model - standardised tests to explore major physiological functions, testing alone or in a pipeline, ethical and scientific consideration, study design, test and data analysis, alternative imaging and methods. Mouse models of human diseases - interests and limitations. Preclinical approaches with mouse models, a first step towards humans.

AXIS 4: Integrated National, European and International initiatives and resources: by, for and at the disposal of the scientific community.

A dedicated meeting webpage was set-up at <https://advanced-school.PHENOMIN.eu/> presenting a detailed overview of course content and objectives. It also has a restricted internal webpage where all course materials and presentations are available for download for all course participants and the course training faculty.

A satisfaction survey was completed online by the participants in order to assess the opinions on the program, organised talks and the organization of the thematic school. Free remarks, were basically classified according to whether they highlighted a strong point, points for improvement or negative points. The complete result of the satisfaction survey is annexed to this document (Annexes 3 and 4). A follow-up was done for the second training school (2019) after half a year, inquiring about its usefulness in their current research projects.

3. Information about the schools

Programmes & special topics

In the 2017 programme (Annex 1), the Scientific Committee has focused on current emerging themes and new concepts, from AXIS 1 and AXIS 3, mainly: CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing, genetically modified rats, impact of the environment on the functional analysis of the genome – Immune system and health status of breeding - Cancer-reproducibility of data - ethics and animal welfare).

In the context of translational research in oncology, the use of the mouse model is today evident with xenografts, or transplants in humanized mice, the study of host-cell relationships in cancer cells, the study of reactions linking cancer and the immune system,

spontaneous or induced tumours (by radiation, chemically or genetically), the longitudinal follow-up of these models by imaging techniques identical to those used in human patients or the approach of new therapies. The "Immunity and cancer" theme was represented and debated by different lectures, given by B. Malissen "Mutagenesis to decipher the mouse immune system", J. Jonkers "Mouse models for cancer", M. Malissen "Immunophenotyping", J. Potter "Aging phenotyping" and S. Lerondel "Imaging and pre-clinical applications". Good practices in the use of the mouse model in oncology and cancerology have been particularly strong in the field of oncology.

In the 2019 programme (Annex 2), the Scientific Committee focused again on current emerging themes and new concepts, from AXIS 1 and AXIS 3, mainly: CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing, genetically modified rats, impact of the environment on the functional analysis of the genome, effect of the microbiota and impact in experimental mouse models, stimulation of the immune system and health status of breeding, ethics and animal welfare.

The "Immunity, Microbiota and Experimental Mouse Models" theme was first introduced by A Zarubica "Mouse models of human diseases and bio confinement" and by G. Pavlovic "Microbiota and experimental mouse models of human disease"; and then represented and debated by different lectures and by a really instructive round-table discussion, proposed successively S. Ganal-Vonarburg "The impact of maternal microbiota on the function of the newborn immune system", all the experts over the round-table discussion addressing "Dirty mice and/or standardization?", M. Schwarzer

“Microbiota-host cross-talk in the juvenile growth and food allergy: lessons from gnotobiotic mouse models” and H. Luche “Immuno-phenotyping of mouse models in the Cytomics era”.

Participants

Participants were both industrial and academic researchers, ranging from Master students to Postdoctoral fellows, scientists and clinicians who use mice as an animal model for their scientific research. **The 2017 edition** of PHENOMIN Advanced Training School involved a total of 26 speakers from 10 leading institutions across Europe and involving PHENOMIN and INFRAFRONTIER members, as well as external experts from among the organiser’s wider network.

In total, 34 registrations were received and 31 participants (3 cancellations) attended the training school; the audience consisted of 26 PhD students, 3 researchers and 2 Master students from France, Germany, UK, Switzerland, Czech Republic and Hungary.

Like the previous edition, the 2019 course involved a total of 27 speakers from leading institutions across Europe and involving PHENOMIN and INFRAFRONTIER members but also external experts from among the organizer's wider network networks from France, Switzerland, Spain, UK and Czech Republic.

27 Experts / 6 European countries

PHENOMIN and INFRAFRONTIER

Switzerland, Spain Netherlands, UK
S Ganal-Rondenbourg, J.Hager, J. Jonkers, I. Mansuy, L. Montoliu, L. Santos, M. Schwarzer, S. Wells

France
X. Montagutelli, JL Mandel,

PHENOMIN's team
-B. Malissen, H. Luche, A. Zarubica (CIPHE)
-A. Ayadi, MC. Birling, E. Bedu, G. BouAbout, I. Goncalves, H. Jacobs, H. Meziane, G. Pavlovic, M. Selloum, T. Sorg, L. Vasseur, O. Wendling (ICS)
-S. Lerondel (TAAM)

phenomin
EXCELLENCE IN MOUSE PHENOGENOMICS

In total, 21 registrations were received and 18 participants attended (3 cancellations, including 1 at the last minute); the audience was composed of 10 PhD students, 5 researchers, 1 engineer and 2 Master students; 37% of the participants came from French laboratories and 26% from the Czech Republic. The others came from 5 other European and assimilated countries (Switzerland). Altogether attendees were from all coming from 7 different countries France, Germany, Poland, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, and Czech Republic.

4. Outcomes and feedback

The whole assessment was discussed with the scientific and organizational committees in order to take stock of the improvements to be made in the framework of a future session, the school being recurrent every two years. The PHENOMIN Advanced School was an opportunity for participants to discuss their research in detail with experts in the field. Thanks to the feedback from the satisfaction survey of the 2015 edition, we had adjusted the program by favouring free time for informal discussions with experts and among participants with success. Additionally, one of the main objectives was to develop innovative concepts and to open the field of reflection of the participants, the survey's analysis showed that the participants had appreciated this part, and were able to make it their own.

In the 2017 edition, 87 % of the participants filled in the feedback survey. 93% of the attendees considered that the programme had been respected, and considered the PHENOMIN Advanced School as useful and very useful (97%). The satisfaction survey and the participant's comments highlighted that the programme was still too dense for them; they suggested reducing the number of oral presentations to give time to assimilate the new concepts, having even more time after the lectures for questions and discussions, favouring basic courses rather than analyses from research work, and having even more discussion groups around animal research (as was done during the afternoon workshops of the programme). The interaction was very good, as 100% considered the atmosphere to be good, and 100% of participants were able to establish professional contacts either with experts (17%), other participants (17%), or both experts and participants (78%). **(Annex 3).**

In the 2019 edition, 100% of the participants filled in the feedback survey. 100% of participants are absolutely satisfied and 100% affirmed that the school met their expectations. Thanks to the survey analysis from 2017, basic courses and short lectures were incorporated, and workshops involving more collective brainstorming and feed backs than individual ones on concrete case studies were added. The feedback on this kind of workshops was very positive. Participants learned a lot about genome editing strategy, experimental design strategy in phenotyping, and data analysis, including statistical aspects, which fulfilled their initial requests (50% of the audience asked for a better understanding of the biases of data analysis and to discuss the reproducibility of data). The workshop on defining cut-off points on harmful phenotypes was also widely appreciated.

Feedback indicated that the program was fairly well-balanced, but that opinions differed widely on the issue. They suggested having even more time after the lectures for questions and discussions, and for workshops and "personal" discussions around their own topics. They would have appreciated it if a small group of experts (2-3) had stayed with each working group (5-6 participants) throughout the week. **(Annex 4).**

About 6 to 8 months later, the participants were surveyed again with the help of a directed on-line questionnaire to find out if the PHENOMIN School has enabled them to make progress in their research work, in concrete terms (only done for 2019 edition). Only 5 attendees had answered and 80% of them indicated that the school had a significant impact on their professional work mainly in the analysis and interpretation of the model data they used.

Overall, given the way you work with the mouse model in a professional situation, would you say that the school has had...

5. *Future plans*

CERBM-GIE (Phenomin-ICS) plans to engage the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (**EFPIA**) actively in teaching, dissemination among their partners and possibly sponsoring. Globally, in 2019 no sponsoring had been actively requested, and no sponsoring had been requested to EFPIA. Two initiatives funded by Europe namely, a COST action on calcification of soft tissue disease (**EuroSoftCalc.net**) and **PAIN-net** on neuropathic pain (<http://www.pain-net.eu/>) had been registered on the website as sponsors only to ensure that the registration of their students/researchers could be possible. Unfortunately, nobody from these 2 programs had attended because of an administrative problem for funding the travellers. In this respect it is worth mentioning that EFPIA expressed their interest and intent to also actively participate in a new EC funded project INFRAFRONTIER partners secured under leadership of the Autonomous University Barcelona. This Knowledge Alliance project aims to develop a university curriculum and master study program for mouse pathologists (**Pathbio.org**). As part of this development work new innovative training materials will be developed that will support future PHENOMIN training schools.

6. Annexes:

phenomin

European advanced school for mouse phenogenomics

2nd edition
June 12th - 16th 2017
Château du Liebfrauenberg,
Alsace, France

INTERACTION WITH EXPERTS
METHODS SHARE OF KNOWLEDGE
SCIENTIFIC AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN
INNOVATION - ETHICS AND WELFARE

Good practices regarding the use of mouse models for biomedical research

<https://advanced-school.phenomin.eu>

2nd edition
June 12th - 16th 2017
Château du Liebfrauenberg,
Alsace, France

TABLE OF CONTENT :

OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRAM	2
SCHEDULE: DAY 1	3
SCHEDULE: DAY 2	4
SCHEDULE: DAY 3	5
SCHEDULE: DAY 4	6
SCHEDULE: DAY 5	7
SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE.....	8
STEERING COMITTEE	8
ORGANIZATION TEAM.....	8
SPEAKERS BIOSKETCHES	9
SUPPORTED BY.....	39
PARTICIPANT’S ABSTRACTS	43
PRACTICAL INFORMATIONS.....	59
ATTENDEES EMAILS.....	60
SPEAKERS AND ORGANIZERS EMAILS.....	61

2nd EUROPEAN ADVANCED SCHOOL FOR MOUSE PHENOGENOMICS

The mouse phenogenomics and the good practices regarding the use
of mouse models for scientific research

OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRAM

Day 1: **Mouse genetics**

Basic overview of laboratory mouse genetics / Advanced mouse genetics programs: European and international new programs.

Day 2: **Mutagenesis**

CRISPR 9 genome editing *in vivo* / Mouse model for decipher the immunity / Mouse models for cancer research

Day 3: **Functional tests in mouse models / Advancing human health**

Standardized exploration of physiological functions, scientific and ethical considerations, study design, analysis and data management, alternative imaging method tests / Preclinical approaches with mouse models, a first step toward the man, interests and limits

Day 4 **Animal Science / Ethics and welfare**

Health, impact on functional studies, increasing safe, colony management and genetically drift / Impact of the mouse gut microbiota / Good practice for good results Workshop: welfare assessment of genetically engineering mouse models

Day 5: **Advanced programs in mouse phenogenomics, initiatives and resources**

National, European and International Integrated Resources: by, for and available to the scientific community / Improving bioscience reporting and data robustness: ensure the reproducibility of pre-clinical studies

SCHEDULE: DAY 1

Monday June 12nd

Day 1: Mouse genetics

Basic overview of laboratory mouse genetics / Advanced mouse genetics programs: European and international new programs.

11:00 AM	Bus leaves Strasbourg's train station to school location
12:00 PM - 1:00 PM	Welcome
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM - 2:30 PM	Introduction (Y. Hérault, PHENOMIN-ICS)
2:30 PM - 3:30 PM	Laboratory Mouse Genetics: basic overview (L. Montoliu, CNB-CSIC)
3:30 PM - 4:30 PM	Advanced Mouse Genetics Programs (Y. Hérault, PHENOMIN-ICS)
4:30 PM - 5:00 PM	Break
5:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Workshop: group 1 - 15 participants max/3-4 experts. Short presentation of scientific project and scientific issue/question/problematic
7:00 PM - 7:30 PM	Free
	Dinner

Tuesday June 13rd

Day 2: Mutagenesis

CRISPR 9 genome editing *in vivo* / Mouse model for decipher the immunity/ Mouse models for cancer research

8:30 AM - 9:00 AM	Mutagenesis: good practices (G. Pavlovic, PHENOMIN-ICS)
9:00 AM - 10:30 AM	CRISPR/Cas9 and other nucleases -Applications and future perspectives (MC. Birling, PHENOMIN-ICS and L. Teboul, MRC)
10:30 AM - 11:00 AM	Break
11:00 AM - 12:00 PM	The use of viral vector for mouse mutagenesis and/or for delivery of gene editing by nuclease (F. Piguet, IGBMC)
12:00 PM - 1:00 PM	Mutagenesis to decipher the mouse immune system (B. Malissen, PHENOMIN-CIPHE)
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
02:00 PM- 03:00 PM	Mouse model for cancer (J. Jonkers, NKI)
3:00 PM - 4:00 PM	Genetic modification and its impact on phenotyping data, i.e, mouse model validation (G. Pavlovic, PHENOMIN-ICS)
4:30 PM - 5:00 PM	Break
5:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Workshop: group 2 - 15 participants max/3-4 experts. Short presentation of scientific project and scientific issue/question/problematic
7:00 PM - 7:30 PM	Free
	Dinner

SCHEDULE: DAY 3

Wednesday June 14th

Day 3: Functional tests in mouse models / Advancing human health

Standardized exploration of physiological functions, scientific and ethical considerations, study design, analysis and data management, alternative imaging method tests / Preclinical approaches with mouse models, a first step toward the man, interest and limits

8:30 AM - 9:00 AM	Functional exploration in mouse models: good practices (T. Sorg , PHENOMIN-ICS)
9:00 AM - 9:30 AM	Strategies for improving reproducibility with <i>in vivo</i> studies (P. Reilly, PHENOMIN-ICS)
9:30 AM - 10:00 AM	Statistical analysis (L. Vasseur, PHENOMIN-ICS)
10:00 AM - 10:30 AM	Imaging and pre clinical applications (S. Lerondel, PHENOMIN-TAAM)
10:30 AM - 11:00 AM	Break
11:00 AM - 11:30 AM	Primary phenotyping of mouse embryos (O. Wendling, PHENOMIN-ICS)
11:30 AM - 12:00 PM	How to phenotype new born and juvenil mice ? (E. Durand, UPJV)
12:00 PM - 12:30 PM	NeuroBehavior and sensory organ phenotyping (H. Meziane, PHENOMIN-ICS)
12:30 PM - 1:00 PM	Aging phenotyping (P. Potter, MRC)
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM - 4:00 PM	Workshop: group 3 - 15 participants max/3-4 experts. Short presentation of scientific project and scientific issue/question/problematic
4:00 PM - 5:00 PM	Break
5:00 PM - 6:30 PM	Retransmission of Informal discussions from workshop session in groups: more important feed back to be adressed
6:30 PM	Diner

Thursday June 15th

Day 4: Animal Science / Ethics and welfare

Health, impact on functional studies, increasing safe, colony management and genetically drift / Impact of the mouse gut microbiota / Good practice for good results Workshop: welfare assessment of genetically engineering mouse models

9:30 AM - 10:30 AM	Tips, Tools and Techniques to secure your mice projects (A. Ayadi, PHENOMIN-ICS)
10:30 AM - 11:00 AM	Break
11:00 AM - 11:30 AM	Immunophenotyping (M. Malissen, PHENOMIN-CIPHE)
11:30 AM - 12:30 PM	Health status, bioconfinement, and microbiota impact on phenotyping (C.Fremond, PHENOMIN-TAAM)
12:30 PM - 1:00 PM	Crucial complementary aspects of functional analysis: anatomic pathology of the mouse (H. Jacobs, PHENOMIN-ICS)
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM - 3:00 PM	The Collaborative Cross, applied to the infectious disease susceptibility (X. Montagutelli, Institut Pasteur)
3:00 PM - 4:00 PM	Animal models are valid to uncover disease mechanisms (Wurst W, HMZ ¹)
4:00 PM - 4:30 PM	Welfare assessment of genetically engineered mouse models (I.Goncalves, PHENOMIN-ICS)
4:30 PM - 5:00 PM	Break
5:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Workshop: "Ethics and welfare assessment of genetically engineered mouse models" - Practical illustrations- workshop session
7:00 PM- 7:30 PM	Free Dinner

Friday June 16th

Day 5: Advanced programs in mouse phenogenomics, initiatives and resources

National, European and International Integrated Resources: by, for and available to the scientific community / Improving bioscience reporting and data robustness: ensure the reproducibility of pre-clinical studies

- | | |
|---------------------|--|
| 8:30 AM- 09:00 AM | European resources : General overview
(Mohammed Selloum, PHENOMIN-ICS) |
| 9:00 AM- 09:30 AM | Gencodys consortium and mouse models for cognitive dysfunction
(Y. Hérault, PHENOMIN-ICS) |
| 9:30 AM- 10:00 AM | Infrafrontier Research Infrastructure
(M. Hagn, HMZ ² -INFRAFRONTIER) |
| 10:00 AM- 11:00 AM | Data integration (AM. Mallon, MRC) |
| 11:00 AM- 11:30 AM | Break |
| 11:30 AM- 12:00 PM | Improving Bioscience Research Reporting: The ARRIVE Guidelines
(I. Goncalves, PHENOMIN-ICS) |
| 12:00 PM - 01:00 PM | Round table: debrief, satisfaction survey, opened discussions on 3
selected major points. |
| 1:00 PM - 2:00 PM | Lunch |
| 2:00 PM | Bus leaves school location to Strasbourg's train station |

phenomin

2nd edition

June 12th - 16th 2017

Château du Liebfrauenberg,
Alsace, France

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Cécile Fremond, PhD, Veterinarian, Director of the "Centre de transgénèse, archivage et modèle animal" or the Center of Transgenesis, Archiving and Animal Model (PHENOMIN-TAAM), CNRS

Yann Hérault, PhD, Director of the "Institut Clinique de la Souris" or Mouse Clinical Institute (PHENOMIN-ICS), INSERM-CNRS-University of Strasbourg

Bernard Malissen, PhD, Director of the "Centre d'immuno-phénogénomique" or the Center of Immuno-Phenogenomics (PHENOMIN-CIPHE), INSERM-University of Aix-Marseille

Patrick Reilly, PhD, Head of the phenotyping department (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Guillaume Pavlovic, PhD, Head of the genetic engineering and model validation department (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Mohammed Selloum, PhD, Project coordination and management of European programs (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Tania Sorg
PhD, Chief operating officer (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Laurent Vasseur
Head of management information department (PHENOMIN-ICS)

STEERING COMMITTEE

Abdel Ayadi, PhD, Head of the mouse services department (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Marie-Christine Birling, PhD, Associate Head of the genetic engineering and model validation department (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Isabelle Goncalves, DMV, Veterinarian and Manager of ethic and welfare (PHENOMIN-ICS)

ORGANIZATION TEAM

Elodie Bedu
PhD, Manager in business development and training (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Joelle Pensavalle
Administrative Assistant (PHENOMIN-ICS)

Philippe Schmitt
PhD, Project Manager of the French distributed infrastructure CELPHEDIA (PHENOMIN-ICS)

AYADI, ABDEL

Thursday, June 15th, 9:30 am

“Tips, Tools and Techniques to secure your mice projects”

Dr. Abdel Ayadi (Ph.D.) is Manager of the mouse facility at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). Abdel Ayadi received his Ph.D. degree in molecular biology from the University of Strasbourg in 2000. Between 2000 and 2007, he worked as project manager in the field of mouse transgenesis in both industry (Deltagen Europe, Genoway) and academia (ICS). Since 2008, Abdel Ayadi has been in charge of the ICS Mouse support service department (2400 m², 45 000 mice) for ICS operations including housing, phenotyping, breeding, embryo microinjection and cryopreservation.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Tuesday, June 13th, 9:00 am

“CRISPR/Cas9 and other nucleases – Applications and Future Perspectives”

Dr. Marie-Christine Birling (Ph.D.) is Head associate of the Genetic Engineering and Model Validation department at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). She did her Ph.D. in 1994, in Dr Jean-Louis Nussbaum’s lab (Centre de Neurochimie, Strasbourg), and then worked as a post-doctoral Fellow, in Dr Jack Price’s lab (SmithKline Beecham Pharmaceuticals, Harlow, UK). In 1997, she was appointed Research Associate in Prof. Peter Brophy’s lab (University of Edinburgh, UK) and moved back to France in 2002 to join Dr Christopher Henderson’s lab, (IBDM, Marseille, France). She entered the ICS in 2003 and has been in charge of the Genetic Engineering team. Marie Christine Birling is responsible for the establishment of more than 1000 alleles using standard technologies and developing CRISPR/Cas9 approaches. She was appointed to her current position in 2008.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Wednesday, June 14th, 11:30 am

“How to phenotype new born and juvenile mice”

Dr. Estelle Durand (Ph.D.) is associate professor and researcher at the Jules Verne University (Picardy, France) since 2016. Studying neurosciences at the Pierre Marie Curie University (UPMC, Paris) , she entered Jorge Gallego’s team to explore phenotyping methods of murine models of Congenital Central Hypoventilation Syndrome (Ondine’s Curse) and obtained her Ph.D. degree in Neuropsychology in 2005. Then, Estelle worked 2 years at Pierre Descartes University (Paris, France) as coordinator of a pilot European interdisciplinary Ph.D. program. Selected to follow the prestigious HEC Challenge+ program in 2008, Estelle co-founded PhenoPups SAS (2010) and became its CEO (2012-2016). This company is an exclusive Preclinical Pediatric Contract Research Organization, focused on new effective methodologies to characterize developmental rat and mouse models and to perform pediatric drug screenings. Its current research project, in the first ever joint university-INERIS research unit, called PériTox (Périnatalité et Risques Toxiques), is currently focused on impacts of perinatal exposure to toxic factors (pesticides) and physical factors (notably the electromagnetic fields (EMFs) generated by mobile phones, and moderate thermal stress) in the environment on the health of newborns and young children – particularly the effects on vital physiological functions involved in maintaining the energy balance (sleep, thermoregulation, respiration, digestion, etc.).

University of Picardy Jules Verne

Thursday, June 15th, 11:30 am

“Health status, bioconfinement and microbiota impact on phenotyping”

Dr. Cécile Fremond (Veterinarian, IR, CNRS, TAAM Director since January 2014, succeeding Dr. Yann Hérault) is Doctor of veterinary medicine from the National Veterinary School of Nantes since 1997. After private practice experience near Orleans in France (domestic animals and horses), she joined the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS) in 1999 as the TAAM vet. At the same time, she prepared a Ph.D. in the domain of innate immunology, to understand the role of receptors and signaling pathways involved in the immune response to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. She obtained, in 2014, a French veterinarian diploma in Science and Medicine of Laboratory Animals at the National Veterinary School of Toulouse (CEAV SMA, Certificat d’Etudes Approfondies Vétérinaires).

PHENOMIN-TAAM

Thursday, June 15th, 4:00 pm

“Welfare assessment of genetically engineered mouse models”

Friday, June 16th, 11:30 am

“Improving Bioscience Research Reporting: The ARRIVE Guidelines”

Dr. Isabelle Goncalves (Veterinarian at the Institut Clinique de Souris, ICS) is Doctor of veterinary medicine since 2007 (Lyons Vet School). She subsequently completed a clinical internship in exotic pets and wild species in Belgium. After 2 years of private practice, she joined the ICS in 2009 and thanks to her expertise, she obtained a French veterinarian diploma in Science and Medicine of Laboratory Animals (CEAV SMAL, Certificat d’Etudes Approfondies Vétérinaires) in 2014. Isabelle is now ICS vet which means being responsible for health monitoring, clinical follow-up of the 45 000 mice and 200 rats, president of the local ethics committee, responsible for animals and biological material import-export service, member of the animal welfare body.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Friday, June 16th, 9:30 am

“Infrafrontier Research Infrastructure”

Dr. Michael Hagn (Ph.D., MBA) works for the INFRAFRONTIER GmbH based in Munich, which coordinates activities of the INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure. He has responsibilities for business development, alliance management and project management. Michael has twelve years of experience in the development and management of EU funded research infrastructures project covering the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) and its successful incorporation into the INFRAFRONTIER operation. Before joining EMMA in 2005 he worked as senior scientist gene discovery for the Munich based biotech company GPC, held a postdoctoral position at the MRC Mammalian Genetics Unit in Harwell / UK and did his Ph.D. at the Max Planck Institute for Plant Breeding Research in Cologne.

HZM2 - INFRAFRONTIER

Monday, June 12th, 2:00 pm & 3:30 pm

“Introduction “ & “Advanced Mouse Genetics Programs”

Friday, June 16th, 9:00 am

“Gencodys consortium and mouse models for cognitive dysfunction”

Dr. Yann Hérault (Ph.D.) is Research Director (DR) at the CNRS, the French National Center for Scientific Research. As a biologist and a mouse geneticist by training, he heads the Institut Clinique de la Souris ("Mouse Clinical Institute", MCI/ICS), and is a research group leader at the IGBMC (Institut de Génétique et Biologie Moléculaire et Cellulaire, Strasbourg). He was appointed Deputy Director of IGBMC in February 2014 with Bertrand Seraphin as Director of the Institute. Yann Hérault has worked on mouse development from a genetic approach for more than 20 years. He has developed a series of techniques for chromosomal engineering with the aim of studying gene regulation at genomic level *in vivo*. His current research interests are focused on evaluating the consequences of gene dosage effect and copy number variation in pathological situations such as in Down Syndrome (or Trisomy 21) to propose new therapeutic approaches. Yann Hérault did his Ph.D. degree at the University of Lyon in 1993, and continued with a post-doctoral training at the University of Geneva from 1993 to 1999 working on Hox gene regulation with Pr. Denis Duboule. He was the former Director of the Transgenesis and Archiving of Animal Models (TAAM) unit from late 2007 to early 2014. He was appointed to his current position at ICS in 2010.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Thursday, June 15th, 12:30 pm

“Crucial complementary aspects of functional analysis: anatomopathology of the mouse”

Dr. Hugues Jacobs (Ph.D., I.R) is co-head of the Histopathology and Embryology service of the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). Former student in medicine, he acquired a deep knowledge in Anatomy, Histology, Embryology and Cell Biology. He obtained his Ph.D degree, at the University of Strasbourg in 2009, in Molecular and cell Biology and became co - head of the histopathology service at ICS in 2011. Since, he is principally focused on pathology assessment of genetically engineered adult mice, in the frame of international mouse phenotyping programs, and academic and industrial partnerships. He is also member of local ethics committee since 2012.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Tuesday, June 13th, 3:00 pm

“Mouse model for cancer”

Dr. Jos Jonkers (Ph.D., professor) is currently Head of the Division of Molecular Pathology at the NKI and Professor of Molecular Experimental Oncogenetics and Cancer Therapeutics at Leiden University. He performed his Ph.D. research and postdoctoral research in the group of Dr. Anton Berns at the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI). In 2002, he visited the lab of Allan Bradley at the Sanger Institute during its second postdoctoral fellow to develop platforms for mouse array-CGH. He started his own research group at the NKI in 2003. In 2012 he was elected to EMBO membership and appointed as Head of Molecular Pathology at the NKI. The research of the Jonkers lab is focused on the genetic dissection of human breast cancer through the use of genetically engineered mouse models (GEMMs) and patient-derived xenograft (PDX) models. His group has generated several mouse models for BRCA1/2-associated hereditary breast cancer and E cadherin-mutated invasive lobular breast cancer, which are used for both basic and translational studies focusing on genotype-phenotype correlations, cancer gene discovery and validation, tumor-host interactions, and mechanisms of therapy response and resistance. Recent key discoveries include the identification of multiple mechanisms by which BRCA1/2-deficient tumors acquire resistance to PARP inhibition or platinum drugs, and the development of CRISPR/Cas9-based GEMMs of breast cancer.

NKI (Netherlands Cancer Institute)

Wednesday, June 14th, 10:00 am

“Imaging and pre clinical applications”

Dr. Stéphanie Lerondel (Ph.D.)(IR, CNRS) is in charge of the Imaging Centre for Small Animals (CIPA) that she has created in 2002; the CIPA being one of the three departments of the UPS44-TAAM-CNRS in Orléans. She began her biology training as an agronomy engineer and in 2000, she had defended her Ph.D. on research in the development of *in vivo* imaging strategies. She completed her training with a Prof MS degree in Quality Assurance specialized in imaging QA in biopharmaceutical research, followed by a post-doc in pharmacotoxicology in an international CRO in Lyon. At CIPA department, Stéphanie Lerondel has implemented *in vivo* X-ray, SPECT, PET bioluminescence, fluorescence, echography and photoacoustic imaging under controlled sanitary conditions, to meet the requirements of the scientific community in fundamental biology, biomedical research and pharmaceutical development. In addition, Stéphanie provides specialized training courses in imaging techniques on living animals.

PHENOMIN-TAAM

Tuesday, June 13th, 2:00 pm

“Mutagenesis to decipher the mouse immune system”

Dr. Bernard Malissen (Ph.D., Professor) is a Research Director (DRCE) at the CNRS, the French National Center for Scientific Research. He heads the Centre d'Immunophénotypage CIPHE in Marseille. He is leader of a research group at the Centre d'Immunologie de Marseille-Luminy (Immunology center) (CIML). Dr Malissen obtained his Ph.D. degree at the University of Aix-Marseille and joined the CNRS in 1980 the same year. His team has contributed to the molecular and structural analysis of the T cell antigenreceptor (TCR) transduction cassette, the molecular basis of T cell development and the genetic dissection of T cell and dendritic cell functions. Using knock-in mice and proteomic approaches, he systematically dissected the proximal elements of the TCR transduction cassette. More recently, his research interests have also focused on dendritic cells and macrophages. He was the Director of CIML from 1995 to 2005.

PHENOMIN-CIPHE

Thursday, June 15th, 11:00 am

“Immunophenotyping”

Dr. Marie Malissen (Ph.D.) is Research Director (DRCE) at the CNRS, the French National Center for Scientific Research. At the Centre d'Immunophénotypage (CIPHE) in Marseille, she co-leads with Bernard Malissen, a team that uses genetics and proteomics to dissect the molecular basis of T cell activation. Dr Marie Malissen obtained her Ph.D. degree in 1979 at the University of Bordeaux, and after acquiring an extensive experience in molecular biology in the laboratory of Leroy Hood (California Institute of Technology), she joined the CNRS in 1984. During the late eighties, she has analyzed the structure of genes coding for major histocompatibility complex molecules and the sophisticated site specific recombinations that dictate the somatic assembly of the genes coding for the T cell antigen receptor (TCR). In the process of comprehensive genetic analysis of T cell activation, Marie Malissen observed that the introduction of partial loss of function mutations in the LAT adaptor resulted in early onset lymphoproliferative disorders that are associated with chronic Th2 inflammation and autoimmunity. Currently, a large part of Marie Malissen's activities is thus devoted to understand the cellular and molecular pathways being at the basis of these fascinating diseases. In frame of the MUGEN European Network of Excellence (2004-2009), based on ENU mutagenesis, Marie Malissen has set up large scale genetic screen aiming at identifying genes involved in lymphoproliferative disorder, neutropenia and LAT pathology. Since 2012, Marie Malissen is the Head of the Immunophenotyping Core facility and Cryopreservation Core facility of the (CIPHE).

PHENOMIN-CIPHE

Friday, June 16th, 10:00 am

“Data integration”

Dr. Ann-Marie Mallon (Ph.D.) is Head of BioComputing at the Mammalian Genetics Unit (MGU) of the Medical Research Council (MRC) in Harwell, UK. She did her Ph.D. in Computational Biology at the University of Manchester in 2004, being at the same time a research assistant specialized in bioinformatics at MRC Harwell. After a two-year postdoc in that field, Anne-Marie Mallon has been appointed Deputy Head of Bioinformatics at MRC Harwell in 2005. Since 2010, she has been the Programme Leader of the Mammalian Genetics Unit at MRC Harwell. Her group develops computational methods to explore the large volumes of data generated by their projects and disseminate the results to the wider scientific community. That programme is coordinated by three main groups focusing on analysing their mouse phenotyping data, applications of computational biology and systems imaging.

MRC Harwell

Wednesday, June 14th, 12:00 pm

“NeuroBehavior and sensory organ phenotyping”

Dr. Hamid Meziane (Ph.D.) is Head of the Behavioural and Cognitive Neuroscience phenotyping platform at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). He received his Ph.D. at the University of Aix-Marseille I. He is mainly interested in studying the neurobiology of behaviour, including pathophysiological mechanisms leading to neurodegenerative disorders, using behavioural, pharmacological, and genetic approaches. He is manager of the platform since 2002, and aims i) to provide behavioural phenotyping services for French academic laboratories, European consortia and pharmaceutical or biotech companies, ii) to develop new assays/protocols to better characterize abnormalities in animal models of human diseases. He has been deeply involved in international programs dedicated to establish and standardize behavioural phenotyping assays to reliably analyse phenotypes consecutive to genetic manipulation in the mouse (EUMORPHIA, EUMODIC, ...) and currently the International Mouse phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) designed to decipher the genome function, and the recently closed GENCODYS program which aimed to understand genetic and epigenetic causes of Cognitive disabilities and to screen for potential therapeutics.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Thursday, June 15th, 2:00 pm

“The Collaborative Cross, applied to the infectious disease susceptibility”

Dr. Xavier Montagutelli (Veterinarian, DVM, Ph.D.) is a Research Director (DR) at the Institut Pasteur in Paris which he has joined in 1987. He has been heading the Animal Facilities of the Institut Pasteur since 1996. He is now heading the Mouse Genetics Laboratory. He did his Ph.D. on the use of mouse interspecific crosses for the genetic analysis of complex traits. He has been a visiting investigator at The Jackson Laboratory in 1994-5. He has developed a mouse genetic reference population, the Interspecific Recombinant Congenic Strains, which he used to dissect genes controlling skull morphology and infertility. For the past 15 years, his research has focused on the genetic control of resistance to infectious diseases in mouse models including Plague, Salmonella, Rift Valley fever virus and more recently Dengue and Zika viruses. He has imported at the Institut Pasteur a subset of the Collaborative Cross and is promoting its use to dissect multigenic traits and study the influence of genetic background.

Institut Pasteur

Monday, June 12th, 2:30 pm

“Laboratory Mouse Genetics: basic overview”

Dr. Lluís Montoliu (Ph.D. , biologist, geneticist and biotechnologist) is CSIC Research Scientist at the Spanish National Centre for Biotechnology (CNB) in Madrid, where he has been leading his laboratory since 1997. He joined in 2007 the Biomedical Research Networking Center on Rare Diseases (CIBERER-ISCI) as Group Leader, where he was appointed in 2016 coordinator of the CIBERER Neurosensory Disorders area and member of the CIBERER Steering committee. He is also Honorary Professor at the Autonomous University of Madrid since 1998, and Director of the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA/INFRAFRONTIER) Spanish node since 2007. His lab is interested in understanding how genes are organized within mammalian genomes and has used different genetically-modified animals (mostly mice and zebrafish) to investigate the role of several non-coding DNA regulatory elements. He has been a leading contributor of the technology of artificial-chromosome-type transgenes. He has also generated numerous animal models of human rare diseases, such as albinism. Recently, he has pioneered the use of CRISPR-Cas9 tools in mice for the functional understanding of DNA regulatory elements and the production of new mouse models of different types of albinism. He is a member of the CSIC Ethics Committee since 2006 and of the ERC Ethics Panel since 2013. In 2006, he founded the International Society for Transgenic Technologies (ISTT) for which he has served as President from inception to 2014. He currently serves at the board of additional scientific societies: IMGS, ESPCR and IFPCS.

CNB-CSIS

Tuesday, June 13th, 8:30 am

“Mutagenesis: good practices”

Tuesday, June 13th, 12:00 pm

“ Genetic modification and its impact on phenotyping date, i.e. mouse model validation”

Dr. Guillaume Pavlovic (Ph.D.) is Head of the Genetic Engineering and Model Validation Department at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). Guillaume Pavlovic received his Ph.D. in 2004 from the University of Nancy on the evolution of mobile bacterial elements. Then, he joined genOway, one of the leading companies in the generation of customized and ready-to-use genetically modified mouse and rat models, where he was in charge to develop and improve the molecular biology department. He started at ICS in 2007 as project manager for industrial customer’s mouse model projects and was appointed to his current position in 2008. He is now in charge of the generation and validation of genetically engineered mouse models for French academic laboratories, European consortia and pharmaceutical or biotech companies, and the development of innovative tools in mouse and rat mutagenesis and transgenesis.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Tuesday, June 13th, 11:00 am

“The use of viral vector for mouse mutagenesis and/or for delivery of gene editing by nuclease”

Dr. Françoise Piguet (Ph.D.) is a Post-Doctoral Fellow in the research team of Dr. Hélène Puccio at the Institut de Génétique et Biologie Moléculaire (IGBMC). She heads the platform of phenotyping and stereotaxic delivery of the Translational medicine and neurogenetics department of the IGBMC. Dr. Piguet obtained her Ph.D. in the University of Paris V and then joined IGBMC in 2013. Since 2006, she contributed to the field of neurodegenerative diseases and development of gene therapy approaches based on the use of AAV first on metachromatic leukodystrophy, Huntington and Friedreich Ataxia. She also used AAV and viral vectors to generate mouse models of Human diseases.

IGBMC

Wednesday, June 14th, 12:30 am

“Aging phenotyping”

Dr Paul K. Potter (Ph.D.), is Head of Disease Model Discovery service in the Mammalian Genetics Unit (MGU) of the Medical Research Council (MRC) in Harwell, UK. He established the Disease Model Discovery group in 2010 to set up and run the Harwell Ageing Screen, a large-scale mutagenesis screen to identify genes and pathways associated with late onset or age-related disease. This programme is a collaborative effort that is generating novel models of age-related disease and identifying new genes and pathways associated with such diseases. Prior to establishing the programme he was Deputy Scientific Manager of mouse mutagenesis and phenotyping projects at the Mary Lyon Centre, Harwell. Paul has also an active research profile investigating several age-related mutants resulting in renal disease, cardiovascular disease or osteoarthritis. He is the Chairperson for the Shared Ageing Research Materials (ShARM biobank), a member of NC3Rs and BBSRC working groups on ageing resources, a member of the Arthritis UK Centre of Osteoarthritis Pathogenesis (Oxford), and an Honorary Senior Lecturer with the section of Renal and Vascular Inflammation at Imperial College. Paul is also a member of the management board and a work package leader for the MouseAGE COST action. By training he is immunologist having completed a Ph.D. degree at the Royal Post Graduate Medical School in Professor Mark Walport's team, followed by post-doctoral appointments in the Renal unit at Guy's Hospital, the Immunology Unit at St.Mary's Hospital. both studying antigen presentation pathways, before returning to Hammersmith hospital to work on the molecular pathogenesis of SLE. He has worked on the genetics of disease and mouse models of disease for around 20 years.

MRC Harwell

Wednesday, June 14th, 9:00 am

“Strategies for improving reproducibility with *in vivo* studies”

Dr. Patrick Reilly (Ph.D.), originally from Canada, is Head of the Phenotyping Department at Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). He earned his Ph.D. degree in Molecular Biology and Biochemistry in 2002 working at Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory in New York, U.S.A. Since then Dr. Reilly has been generating and phenotyping GEMs for over a decade in Toronto, Zürich, Singapore, and now France. While his main subject of interest has been the genetic etiology of cancers, his studies have touched on aspects of metabolism, gene regulation, embryology, and behaviour. Patrick Reilly joined Phenomin-ICS as Head of Phenotyping in late 2015 where he oversees mouse projects for international consortia as well as industrial and academic clients.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Friday, June 16th, 8:30 am

“European resources: general overview”

Dr. Mohammed Selloum (Pharm.D) is Project Manager of European programs at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). He was trained as an industrial pharmacist, completed by a 8 months training at Eli Lilly (Fegersheim) in the quality assurance department after his graduation (1998). Then, from 1999 to 2001, he worked at Strasbourg Hospital as a resident in the clinical biochemistry and emergency department (headed by Prof. Chambon). He was in charge of medical validation of biochemistry analysis as well as participating in the establishment of GBEA (clinical chemistry lab accreditation). Mohammed Selloum joined the ICS in 2001 as an assistant at the Metabolism and Biochemistry.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Wednesday, June 14th, 8:30 am

“Functional exploration in mouse models: good practices”

Dr. Tania Sorg (Ph.D.) is Chief Operating Officer of the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS) . Tania Sorg received her Ph.D. degree in Molecular and Cellular Biology from the University of Strasbourg in 1996. Between 1996 and 2001, she worked as a scientist and project leader at Transgene, Strasbourg, in the field of Gene therapy. Between 2001 and 2003, she became Head of the Technology department at Deltagen Europe, Strasbourg, working in the drug discovery field. She joined the ICS in May 2003 to manage the facility (general management of 3 departments composed of 13 teams, total of about 100 persons), including the establishment and supervision of scientific projects, human resources & equipment management, and contribution to the strategic and financial decisions of the Institute. She supervised also the clinical phenotyping department until 2015, in charge of the functional characterization of mouse models and compound studies, as well as research and development activity.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Tuesday, June 13th, 9:00 am

“CRISPR/Cas9 and other nucleases – Applications and future perspectives”

Dr. Lydia Teboul (Ph.D.) is Head of Molecular and Cellular Biology at the Mary Lyon Centre (MLC) of the Medical Research Council (MRC) in Harwell, UK. She is managing the generation of genetically altered mice, in this large national animal facility that offers support for the use of mice in biomedical research in the UK. She has 19 years of experience of mouse genome engineering, with both classical and genome editing methods. She is introduced the use of the CRISPR/Cas9 system at the MLC in 2013 and now employs these tools in both a high throughput process for the generation of null-mice and a bespoke activity for the generation of point mutations and more complex models. The scale of our use of the system has allowed the team at the MLC to refine protocols to achieve high efficiency of mutagenesis, continuously broadening the range of allele types that can be obtained. They also have defined quality control criteria and reliable protocols to check the mutants generated employing CRISPR/Cas9 tools. Lydia is managing both the production and the technical development aspects of these activities at the MLC.

MRC Harwell

Wednesday, June 14th, 9:30 am

“Statistical analysis”

Laurent Vasseur (IR) is Head of Information Technology team (IT team) at the Institut Clinique de la souris (ICS). He had worked as IT Engineer in a French company and entered ICS in 2002. His mission was to design the information system of the Institute. Through the years, he led the IT team to build the infrastructure to capture and analyze the scientific and administrative data of the ICS departments through web-based applications. These databases cover major activities (genetic engineering, animal facility, phenotyping), as well as transversal fields such as quality control. He has participated in the design of large scale programs (Eumodic, IMPC) as well as IT collaborations with private partners.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Wednesday, June 14th, 11:00 am

“Primary phenotyping of mouse embryos”

Dr. Olivia Wendling (Ph.D.) (IR, CNRS) is co-head of the Histopathology and Embryology service of the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). She obtained her Ph.D. degree, at the University of Strasbourg, in Developmental Biology during which she acquired the anatomical and histological bases to perform integrated analyses of embryonic systems (2000). Then, she entered the CNRS in 2001 as Research Engineer and became co –manager of the histopathology service at IGBMC (Institut de Génétique et Biologie Moléculaire et Cellulaire, Strasbourg), and then at ICS. She focused on the morphological analyze of genetically engineered mice. Olivia Wendling was regularly involved in projects aimed at phenotyping mutants during in utero development. In the frame of the ICS involvement in the European and international mouse phenotyping program, she has developed an embryonic phenotyping pipeline to decipher gene functions through the morphological analyze of fetuses and embryos of the mutant lines that are lethal in utero or peri-natally.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Thursday, June 15th, 3:00 pm

“Animal models are valid to uncover disease mechanisms”

Prof. Wolfgang Wurst (Ph.D.) is Director of the Institute of Developmental Genetics (IDG) at the Helmholtz Zentrum München (HMGU) in Neuherberg and chairholder at the Technical University Munich (TUM). Since September 2009 he is Partner of the DZNE (Deutsches Zentrum für Neurodegenerative Erkrankungen in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft), Site Munich, Germany. Before he was appointed to his current positions at HMGU and TUM in 2002, he was group leader of the group ‘Molecular Neurogenetics’ at the Max-Planck-Institute of Psychiatry in Munich and Junior Research Group Leader at the Department of Mammalian Genetics, GSF Research Center, Neuherberg/Munich. Prof. Dr. Wurst studied Biology/Chemistry at the University of Freiburg, Germany, obtained his Ph.D. degree at the University of Göttingen, Germany, in 1988, and continued with post-doctoral training at the University Göttingen (1988-1989) and the Samuel Lunefeld Research Institute of the Mount Sinai Hospital, Division of Molecular and Developmental Biology, in Canada (1989-1994; headed by A. Joyner). He has longstanding expertise in the development and application of novel gene editing technologies for *in vivo* gene function analysis (gene trapping, gene targeting, RNA Interference, TAL-effector nucleases, Zinc-finger-nucleases, CRIPSR/Cas). In this context he was among others coordinator of the European Conditional Mouse Mutagenesis Program (EUCOMM/EUCOMMTools) and is founding member of the International Mouse Knockout Consortium (IKMC) of which he was president in 2010/11. Furthermore, he focuses on the generation and analysis of new human cellular and tissue models as well as animal models for neurological (Dementias, Parkinson’s disease, ALS) and psychiatric diseases (Major depression). **HZM 1**

Organization committee

Dr. Elodie Bedu (Ph.D.) is manager in business development and training at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). She obtained her Ph.D. degree at the University of Lyon, in the field of Integrative Physiology and more especially on the metabolic implication of liver and muscle in thermoregulation process (2002). Then she worked as a post-doctoral Fellow: first in Pr. Walter Whali's lab (Center of Integrative Genomics, Lausanne, Switzerland) where she acquired the cellular and molecular bases to perform integrated analyses of gene function in lipid metabolism by using genetic engineering mouse model, and then in Pr. Hubert VIDAL lab's "Human nutrition and diabetes" (CarMeN, Lyon, France). Elodie Bedu joined the ICS in 2008 and managed the metabolism Team in the phenotyping department until 2011. She is now in charge to the set up and to manage training and workshops, to promote the visibility of PHENOMIN-ICS, and to help in finding new users. She is also member of local ethics committee since 2014.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Organization committee

Joelle PENSAVALLE is the executive administrative assistant at the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS). Her mission is to facilitate the success of the direction of ICS and PHENOMIN and support other members of the executive management team. After her University English studies at the University of Strasbourg, Joelle has been employed as administrative assistant in private French companies (ABP technology-vaccitest corporation, Capsugel) and then entered ICS in 2009.

PHENOMIN-ICS

Organization committee

Dr. Philippe Schmitt (Ph.D.) is Project Manager of the distributed Research Infrastructure CELPHEDIA gathering 15 centers in France and covering 3 major families of animal models: non mammalians, rodents and non-human primates. He did his Ph.D. in Molecular Biology at IGBMC Institute in Strasbourg, working on splicing mechanisms. It was followed by a two-year postdoc on a different topic, at the Bacteriology Institute, still in Strasbourg. After his studies, he left academic research to enter a private company over a period of almost 20 years and whose name has changed several times through its history (Appligene, Oncor, Qbiogene, MP Biomedicals). He was in charge of the creation of new products in molecular biology, especially PCR and qPCR, of the production and the quality control of the products manufactured in the facility and was strongly involved in the marketing department. Since 2012, he has taken the position of project manager of CELPHEDIA, coordinating research, technical and administrative actions between the centers partner of CELPHEDIA.

CELPHEDIA

NOTES:

Series of horizontal lines for writing notes.

SUPPORTED BY

INFRAFRONTIER
mouse disease models

EC Horizon2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020
project grant agreement number 730879

Our sponsors

DESIGNER GENES

COME TO CHARLES RIVER FOR YOUR CUSTOM FIT.

We've joined forces with **Phenomin-iCS**, a scientific leader in functional genomics, to deliver a complete solution for mouse and rat models, from creation to validation. Our combined *in vitro* and *in vivo* expertise shapes a broad portfolio of design (ES cell, CRISPR/Cas9, random insertion), breeding and associated services – so you get the most relevant models for your studies. We offer industry-leading germ line transmission, strict quality controls, fast turnaround and a dedicated project manager to guide you through your project. **Learn more at www.criver.com/modelcreation**

EVERY STEP OF THE WAY

phenomin iCS

charles river

www.criver.com

INFRAFRONTIER

mouse disease models

The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

High-quality resources and services for biomedical research

International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium

- First comprehensive catalogue of mammalian gene function
- An engine for discovering the genetic basis for disease
- Open access to data and resources
- Access to positive and negative results

INFRAFRONTIER Resources and Services

Distributed research infrastructure – one face to the customer

www.infrafrontier.eu

ALLEGRE Nicolas

Single cell development in early mouse embryogenesis

ALLEGRE Nicolas, CHAZAUD Claire

The team is interested in cell differentiation during mouse preimplantation. At E3.5, three lineages are present. The primitive endoderm (PrE) cells expressing GATA6 and the epiblast (EPI) cells expressing NANOG are arranged in a « salt and pepper » manner, and are all surrounded by trophectoderm cells.

After analysing Nanog or Gata6 single mutants embryos (Frankenberg, Dev Cell 2011; Bessonard, Development 2014), we are now characterizing Nanog/Gata6 double mutants cell identity in situ (immunofluorescence) and by RTqPCR on single ICMs or single cells (Fluidigm Biomark). Our preliminary results indicate that the ICM of these double mutants seems to be stuck at an early ICM precursor stage. Single-cell RNAseq is planned as well as in vitro cell derivation of stem-like cells.

ARCUCCI Silvia

Role of the class IA PI3K p110 β subunit in pancreatic cancer

Arcucci S., Therville N., Basset C., Vertut A., Guillermet-Guibert J.

Transdifferentiation of pancreatic acinar cells in duct-like cells is at the origin of pancreatic ductal cancer. Previous results of the team demonstrated that while the isoform α of PI3K is necessary for the transformation of acinar cells by oncogenic Kras, the genetic inactivation of the p110 β isoform does not prevent in vivo the formation of ductal structure. However, mutant mice harboring in their pancreas a mutated version of Kras and/or p53 and of inactive p110 β under the control of PDX1 promoter, which is specific of pancreatic progenitor cells, are protected from mutated Kras and p53-induced lethality.

Seen that the function of p110 β in pancreatic cancer cell is unknown, the aim of our project will be to study the role of p110 β in pancreatic cancerogenesis.

BOUSCARY Alexandra

Modulation of sphingolipids as a therapeutic approach in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis.

Alexandra Bouscary, Alexandre Henriques, Jean-Philippe Loeffler

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is a fatal disease characterized by upper and lower motor neuron degeneration. Growing evidence suggests a link between changes in lipid metabolism and ALS. Glucosylceramide (GlcCer), a lipid of the sphingolipids family, is a key lipid in the metabolism of gangliosides. It is possible to modify the metabolism of sphingolipids by pharmacological approach. Indeed, it has been demonstrated in the laboratory that the inhibition of UGCG, which is the enzyme responsible for the synthesis of GlcCer impairs axonal regeneration after sciatic nerve lesion. Sphingolipids and especially ceramides and GlcCer are important for motor axis. In my research project, I seek to verify the effect of the degradation of GlcCer through pharmacological approaches.

COURREGES Christina

Role of the PI3K Vps34 in T cell immunity

Courreges C., Slack E, Schoenfelder P., Bilanges B., Rebello E., Vanhaesebroeck B. and Okkenhaug K.

The class III PI3K Vps34 is highly conserved within eukaryotes and is a key mediator of autophagy and endocytosis in yeast and certain mammalian cell types. To investigate its role in regulatory T cells, we crossed a FoxP3-driven Cre- recombinase mouse to a floxed Vps34 strain. Due to the location of FoxP3 on the X chromosome, female offspring show a “mosaic” phenotype. This allows the study Vps34-sufficient and deficient Treg cells arising from a common environment. To understand the involvement of Vps34 in cell homeostasis and autophagy, we performed flow cytometry analyses, biochemical and in vitro assays. While homozygous Vps34-deficient mice died from a Scurfy-like disease, our results so far could not support the involvement of Vps34 in autophagy or endocytosis in Treg cells.

DERLE Abhishek

Investigating the role of PI3K-C2a in Genomic instability and Cancer

Abhishek Derle, Emilio Hirsch

Unpublished data from our lab also indicate that PI3K-C2 α reduction has a biphasic effect on tumor growth in transgenic mouse model of mammary tumorigenesis. This is caused due to disorganization of mitotic spindle by the loss of kinase-independent scaffolding function of PI3K-C2 α . In view of this background, the principal objective of my doctoral study will be to further investigate the role of PI3K-C2 α in genomic instability and cancer. For this purpose, our laboratory has successfully generated PI3K-C2 α conditional knockout mouse model, which will allow us to appreciate the vital role of this protein in cellular physiology. I am involved in genotyping this cohort of mice followed by collecting blood and bone marrow from these conditional knockout mice for my studies.

JIA Tao

Role of RNA splicing in endothelial cells and the consequences of targeting VEGFR/integrin/FGFR2 signaling pathways on these events

Tao J., Thibault J., Cherine A.F., Subra G., Jean-luc C., Beatrice E.

To better understand whether anti-angiogenic therapies regulate pre-mRNA splicing process events of VEGFR/FGFR/Integrin signaling in endothelium, and whether cell-cell contact (co-culture) between endothelial cells and tumor cells expression SR proteins would affect the signature of RNA splicing form of endothelial cells, We used a multi-pronged approach from biochemical biology, cell biology, chemical biology and especially nano-technology. In this work, we not only gain a better understanding about synergistic/antagonistic functions of VEGFR/FGFR/Integrin signaling networks by which ECM regulates vessel maturation/sprouting, but also identify innovative therapeutic strategies to target pathological angiogenesis and in particular to fight cancer and prevent tumor escape.

JUNG Piotr

Generating Plekhs1 conditiona KO mouse

Piotr Jung

We plan to inject the ES cells obtained from EUCOMM, carrying the PLEKHS1 conditional KO construct, into blastocysts to generate chimeras. The chimeras will need to be bred to establish whether the construct is expressed in their germline. The PLEKHS1 mouse model will be a very powerful tool with which to study PLEKH1 function. Currently it is unclear whether total loss of PLEKHS1 will impact the development or viability of mice. If the mice develop normally and are fully viable it may allow us to use the primary “knock-out-first” allele for experiments. Further crosses of that strain with probasin-Cre x PTENLoxP/LoxP mouse strains could afford the opportunity to investigate in depth the contribution of PLEKHS1 to prostate cancer progression in mice.

KAMPYLI Charis

The cell biological roles of the PI3K-C2 β class II isoform of PI3K

Charis Kampyli

The cell biological and in vivo roles of the PI3K-C2 β class II isoform of PI3K remain largely unknown and no small molecule inhibitors are available for this kinase. Our laboratory has created a knock-in mouse line in which the kinase activity of PI3K-C2 β is constitutively inactivated (Alliouachene et al., 2015), and we are now using this as a tool to dissect the cell biological roles of PI3K-C2 β , using cells derived from these mice.

Our study is focused on: i.) the investigation of the impact of PI3K-C2 β kinase inactivation on cellular processes, such as cellular migration and focal adhesion dynamics, ii.) the characterisation of the upstream and downstream signals emanating from PI3K-C2 β and iii.) linking these observations to in vivo phenotypes in the mice, for example in angiogenesis.

PI3K-Drug Resistance, Isoform Selectivity, and Regulation

Erhan Keles, Denise Rageot, Alexander M. Sele, Matthias P. Wymann

A combination of PI3K isoform-specific inhibitors and conditional genetic approaches is expected to refine the understanding of selective PI3K isoform functions, and to reveal further non-redundant cellular signalling activities of these lipid kinases. Covalent PI3K inhibitors provide an unexplored opportunity to link PI3K isoforms to specific processes in cancer and inflammation using chemical genetics and to develop locally acting, PI3K isoform-selective strategies to inhibit aberrant cellular signalling. Validation of novel covalent inhibitors regarding warhead reactivity and specificity provides a new platform to study PI3K biology and drug resistance mechanism caused by PI3K mutations.

Deciphering a role of p110 α subunit of PI3 kinase in endothelial cell biology

Kobialka P. and Graupera M.

One of the catalytic isoform of the PI3K enzymes – p110 α – is particularly important for endothelial cells (ECs) migration during sprouting angiogenesis. Moreover, global and EC-specific p110 α loss of function leads to lethality due to several vascular abnormalities. The physiological role of PI3K in angiogenesis remains obscure, although there is an evidence for its role in venous-specification. Thus, in order to study the role of PI3K in this process, the EC-specific p110 α LOF and GOF mouse retinas will be analysed using different molecular markers. Moreover, by using the mTmG reporter, we will be able to perform single cell tracking in order to understand the impact of LOF and GOF mutations on arteriovenous markers expression and positioning of ECs within the vasculature.

KOKOCIŃSKA Natasza

Metabolic screening in aging pipeline.

Chambers J.N., Kokocińska N.M.

The metabolic pathways and overall energy homeostasis is an integral system with physiology. Alterations within this tightly regulated & controlled system can result in diseases such as obesity & diabetes, but also affect the ability of other systems to function optimally e.g. renal system, cardiovascular etc. During aging, energy misbalances increase e.g. type 2 diabetes and affect other systems to a greater extent. For this reason, our centre is starting to investigate the role of various genes in the onset and regulation of the aging process focusing on energy balance.

I think that this course will be advantageous for me to further understand the more complete scope from genotype to phenotype with a specific interest in aging studies.

KOPPEROVÁ Dana

Methods of Analysis indels mutations created by CRISPR/Cas9 system

Kopperova D., Beck I., Kopkanova J., Sedlacek R.

CRISPR/Cas9 system is used as a main precise tool for editing genome and elucidate function of the target gene. This system generates double-strand breaks and during the DNA repair it leads to insertions, deletions or substitutions at target sites. To analyse the indels we can use the detection of heteroduplexes created during re-annealing step. One option is detection of heteroduplexes on native PAGE. This is very specific and sensitive and we can distinguish at least 2nt indels. Another option is to analyse PCR product on QIAxcell Advanced system (high-resolution capillary electrophoresis). The recognition of heteroduplexes is very important as a first screening step before the sequencing. The band pattern is stable from G1 generation and native PAGE can be used for regular screening.

KORSÓS Gabriella

Effect of original and five octaves higher music of Bach and Mozart on the behaviour of mice of different genotypes

Korsós G., Brown D. L., Windig-Zavadil C., Rühlicke T, Fekete. S. G.

The importance of acoustic stimuli plays a different role in the life of laboratory rodents. In the present experiments „rodentized" Bach and Mozart music has been used by increasing the pitches to the hearing range of mice (1 kHz-110 kHz). During the first trial twenty adult male (SPF, CD1) mice were used to take ethograms under the effect of the musical stimuli. In the second trial twelve male BALB/c mice were investigated using TiBeSplit open-field equipment. During the music the activity of the animals decreased, but not in the same way in the different genotypes. The effect of rodentized music differs that of the human version and the genotype plays also a role.

KUČERA Jan

Application of image analysis and machine learning in evaluation of subtle differences of microscopical organ structures

Kucera J.

Along with present rapid development of IT hardware and software capabilities arises a new possibility of deeper analysis of quite complicated structure of histological tissue samples. Using these technologies improves the analysis outcome in quantitative manner. Variances of tissue morphology which pathologist differentiate by experience and knowledge can be transferred into numerical values and thus it can be correctly and precisely compared. Various phenotypes in mouse organ structure differs in slight morphology whose differentiation only deeper morphological analysis can elucidate.

MACKINTOSH Albert

Class II Phosphatidylinositide 3-kinases synaptic function and brain development

Mackintosh AI, Kaempf N, Haucke V

Eukaryotic cells express various isoforms of PI3Ks that have been subdivided into three classes. While the role of class I PI3Ks in cell signaling and growth control via receptor-activated synthesis of PIP3 is well studied, much less is known about class II PI3Ks, thought to synthesize PI3,4P2 instead of PI3P to regulate endocytosis and endosomal trafficking as well as nutrient signaling at late endosomes/ lysosomes. Though the class II PI3Ks PI3KC2 α and PI3KC2 β are highly expressed in brain, their function there has been elusive. In my project I use a multifaceted approach based on the analysis of conditional PI3KC2 alpha and PI3KC2 Beta knockout mice, cell imaging and biochemical assays as well as electrophysiology and behavior to study the role of these enzymes in central nervous system neurons.

MARTIN LORENZO Sandra

Genetics and Therapeutics Approaches for counteracting the consequences of 16p11.2 deletion in preclinical models

Sandra Martin Lorenzo S, Chevalier C., Wagner C., Birling M. C., Yalcin, B., and Yann Hérault

The 16p11.2 deletion induces intellectual disabilities and autistic spectrum disorders. This deletion is a consequence of the recombination between two Low Copy Repeat? BP4 and BP5. The search for interactions between the genes in the region genes, brain activity and behavior is crucial to understand the neurocognitive processes that are altered. Candidate genes is particularly difficult because the region showed a high density of genes, the majority of which are important for neurodevelopment. Complementary to human genetic analyzes, animal models have been developed to study the correlation between the phenotype and the genotype.

MUNIZ MORENO Maria del mar

Characterisation of a mouse model carrying the human Dyrk1a missense point mutation T588N with a wild type potential (PM-cWT)

Muñiz M.M., Duchon A., Birling M.C., DubosA., Brault V., Marechal D., and Herault Y

Dyrk1A (Dual specificity Tyrosine Regulated Kinase 1A) is one of the main drivers of the observed neurological phenotypes in Down Syndrome (DS). Overdose of this gene, in both DS patients and mice models overexpressing Dyrk1A, produce deficits in learning, memory, cognition, endocytosis and synaptic function (Duchon et al. 2016). More than a hundred of mutations on DYRK1A have being recorded but in most cases their pathogenicity is unknown. To understand the observed phenotype in a patient with a de novo DyrK1A missense mutation (c.1763C4A, p.Thr588Asn) we will do the phenotypic, molecular and cellular characterisation of a mouse model carrying the mutated Dyrk1A with wild type potential(PM-cWT). In the future we aim to propose a strategy for recovering both normal phenotype and function

NATTARAYAN Vasugi

Roles of phospholipids and regulating enzymes in skeletal muscle under physiological and pathological (myopathy) conditions in vivo.

Vasugi Nattarayan, Jocelyn Laporte

Phosphoinositides (PIs) are key phospholipids that differently tag specific membrane sites and thus regulate intracellular trafficking and signal transduction. Mutations in their regulating enzymes like PI3Ks or phosphatases cause diseases like cancer, neuromuscular defects, etc., Among these, centronuclear myopathies (CNM) are due to mutations in the phosphoinositides phosphatase MTM1 or in the phosphoinositides binding proteins amphiphysin 2 and dynamin 2. However, the regulation and cellular role of this pathway in muscle is not known and the pathological mechanisms leading to the myopathies are not understood. The aim of our research is to study the role of PIs in the pathogenesis of CNM using the mice models which are available in our laboratory that reproduces CNM disease pathology.

PARENTÉ Alexis

Alterations in adiposity and glucose homeostasis in adult overexpressing Gasp-1 mice.

Alexis Parenté, Luce Périè, Fabienne Baraige, Laetitia Magnol and Véronique Blanquet

Myostatin acts as a powerful negative regulator of muscle growth and plays a key role in skeletal muscle homeostasis but can also impact on metabolism. The *Mstn*^{-/-} mice leads to an increase of insulin sensitivity, a decrease of adiposity and a resistance to obesity. Thus, myostatin is a potential therapeutic target to treat insulin resistance. We generated transgenic mice overexpressing Gasp-1, a myostatin inhibitor. Surprisingly, we found that this mice gained weight with age due to an increase in fat mass associated with ectopic fat accumulation and develop an adipocyte hypertrophy, hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, muscle and hepatic insulin resistance. Molecular analyses revealed a deregulation of adipokines and cytokines expression, but also an increase in plasma myostatin levels.

PEREZ Mattia

Spreading of FUS aggregates in Knock-in mice

Perez M, Scekcic-Zahirovic J, Dupuis L

FUS is an RNA-binding protein involved in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and frontotemporal dementia (FTD). FUS loss and gain-of-function mechanisms have been proposed to explain motor neuron degeneration, and protein aggregation is a hallmark of ALS pathology. ALS usually spreads focally from the first affected region (motor cortex) to neighbouring regions according to central nervous system anatomy. The mechanisms underlying the spreading of the clinical phenotype remain unknown. The objective of this work is to determine the role of cortical neurons in the generation and spreading of FUS pathological aggregates and subsequent neurodegeneration, both in FUS knock-in mice as in ALS-FTD patients derived human samples.

RAMOS DELGADO Carmen Fernanda

PI3K isoform-specificity in pancreatic plasticity

Ramos-Delgado CF, Pons E, Thibault B, Guillermet-Guibert J

Previous studies have demonstrated that modulating pancreatic PI3K activity in conditions such as pancreatitis or pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) has noticeable physiological effects. It has been demonstrated that the in vitro inhibition of p110a, a Class I PI3K isoform, prevents the onset of PDAC. In vivo studies are being conducted using a murine model of progressive PDAC to determine the effects of p110a isoform-specific inhibition.

Less is known about the role of other PI3K isoforms, such as Class II b, in either physiological or pathological conditions. In order to determine the role of PI3K-C2b in inflammatory conditions (pancreatitis), a murine model harboring a PI3K-C2b-kinase-inactivation is being used.

REBOLLO GÓMEZ Elena

Vps34-dependent PI3P pools regulation

Rebollo-Gómez E

Vps34/PIK3C3 is the sole member of the class III phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K) and produces PI3P (phosphoinositol 3 phosphate). PI3P is the predominant phosphoinositol in the endosomal compartment. Necessary for endosomal maturation and autophagy, it regulates the subcellular localization of proteins containing PI3P-binding modules, but the contributions of vps34 to PI3P pools directly involved in signalling is still unclear. After characterizing a Vps34 mutant inactivated allele in vitro, I aim to investigate the regulation of Vps34-dependent PI3P pools by certain agonists and its functional implications.

I will measure the effect of insulin stimulation on PI3P levels and if these pools are Vps34 dependent in metabolic cells and tissues derived from our KI inactivated vps34 mice.

SAMSÓ FERRÉ Paula

Class II PI3K and PI3-phosphatase complexes in phosphoinositide conversion

Samsó-Ferré P.

Class II PI 3-kinases, which synthesize PI(3,4)P₂ and PI(3)P at the plasma membrane and endolysosomal system, and myotubularins (MTMR), a family of PI 3-phosphate phosphatases believed to act on PI(3)P and PI(3,5)P₂ and linked to human disease have been suggested to coexist in protein modules. We hypothesize that these class II PI3K/MTMR complexes regulate synthesis and turnover of PI 3-phosphates at the cell surface and/or the endolysosomal system. The goal of my project is to identify and characterize the interaction between class II PI3K and MTMR phosphatases, studying the complex formation, regulation and physiological role. We aim to generate in vivo models to study their relevance in vivo.

SANCHEZ-GUIXE Monica

mTORC1/2-activating genetic alterations confer resistance to PI3K inhibitors but sensitize to mTORC1/2 inhibitor in PDX models

Sánchez-Guixé M., Palafox M., Gris A., Guzmán M., Rodríguez O., Grueso J., Graupera M., Rodon J., Serra V.

PI3K pathway activation is one of the most frequent alterations in breast cancer. Current treatment with specific PI3K-alpha inhibitors (PI3KinH), such as BYL719, shows promising results upon reduction of tumour growth. However, PI3K-matched therapy becomes challenging due to recurrent acquired resistance. Mechanisms of resistance to PI3K-therapy in ER+ breast cancer include mTORC1 activation as a common alteration, a downstream effector of the PI3K pathway. We have characterised a list of 17 PDXs: genomically and to its sensibility towards PI3K inhibitors, and we have selected potential candidates of resistance to PI3K inhibitors. Finally, we propose mTORC1/2 inhibition when alterations activate mTOR, such as TSC1 loss and STK11 mutations.

SANJUAN RUIZ Inmaculada

Pathophysiological mechanisms involved in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis caused by mutations in the FUS gene

Sanjuan-Ruiz I.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis is a fatal neurodegenerative disease affecting upper and lower motor neurons leading to a progressive paralysis and muscular atrophy in patients. The etiology of the disease is not completely understood nor characterised. A minority of the population affected by this disease is due to a mutation in the Fused in Sarcoma (FUS) protein. We have created a FUS knock-in transgenic mouse animal model to identify the pathophysiological mechanisms leading to lower motor neurons death. Through different mutagenesis methods we aim to determine whether FUS mislocalization can be restored, as well as unravel the genetic machinery responsible for motor neurons loss. Identifying new targets could lead to improved and more effective therapeutic strategies.

VORLOVA Barbora

Production of antibodies against mouse native antigens in knockout mice

Vorlova B, Kumpostova D, Sramkova K, Kasperek P, Sedlacek R, Sacha P, Konvalinka J

Laboratory mice are routinely used for antibody production. With increasing number of knockout mice being prepared in order to decipher function of all mouse genes, there is an increasing demand for antibodies against mouse proteins. While antibodies against denatured mouse antigens can be easily prepared using mice, preparation of antibodies against native antigens is impossible. Here we show that antibodies against native mouse antigens could be successfully produced using knockout mice. We immunized prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA, also known as glutamate carboxypeptidase II) knockout mice by native PSMA and subsequently characterized produced antibodies using flow cytometry, ELISA and immunohistochemistry on frozen tissue sections.

WAEGAERT Robin

A transgenic mouse expressing CHMP2Bintron5 mutant in neurons develops histological and behavioural features of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and frontotemporal dementia.

Vernay A, Therreau L, Blot B, Risson V, Dirrig-Grosch S, Waegaert R, Lequeu T, Sellal F, Schaeffer L, Sadoul R, Loeffler JP, René F

Mutations in the charged multivesicular body protein 2B (CHMP2B) are associated with frontotemporal dementia (FTD) and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). To model this syndrome, we generated a transgenic mouse line expressing the human CHMP2Bintron5 mutant in a neuron-specific manner. A longitudinal study revealed progressive gait abnormalities, reduced muscle strength, and decreased motor coordination. CHMP2Bi5 mice died due to generalized paralysis. When paralyzed, signs of denervation were present as attested by altered electromyographic profiles. In addition to the motor dysfunctions, CHMP2Bi5 mice progressively developed FTD-relevant behavioural modifications such as disinhibition, stereotypies, decrease in social interactions and change in dietary preferences.

ZANONCELLO Jasmina

Phosphoinositide 3-kinase Signalling in Oncogenic Vascular Malformations (VMs)

Zanoncello J, Castillo S., Graupera M.

Venous malformations are painful and deforming vascular lesions present from birth. Sclerotherapy, accepted as first-line treatment, is not efficient and targeted therapy remains underexplored. Our aim is to generate a mouse model that mirrors human VM through mosaic expression of *Pik3caH1047R*, a constitutively active mutant of the p110a isoform of PI3K in the embryonic mesoderm. We also report the presence of activating PIK3CA mutations in human VMs. By demonstrating a causal relationship between activating *Pik3ca* mutations and the genesis of VMs, we would like to provide a possible genetic model that mirrors the etiology and development of this human disease, establishing the basis for the use of PI3K-targeted therapies in VMs.

“Neuromuscular phenotypes” assessment in DigiGateTM

Agnieszka Kubik-Zahorodna, Václav Žatecka

Early systems for evaluation of disturbances in animal gait, ink footprint analysis, were recently replaced by automated devices. Nearly all of them base kinematic analysis of movement on video recordings of the animal’s footprints. Some of them serve with possibility to study swim kinematics. But gross of those automated solutions deal with unneglectable confounder in the interpretations of gait deviations caused by differences in walking speed of each animal. DigiGaitTM overcomes this obstruction by applying a treadmill that enables regulation of animal speed. Our facility cooperates with scientists, who study models of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, or fine movement regulation by cannabinoid system to find unique kinematic characterisation of particular central nervous system diseases.

Systems immunology of T cell co-inhibitors associated to SHIP-1

Yunhao ZHAI, Romain Roncagalli, Bernard Malissen.

My PhD project mainly focus on the SHIP-1 knock-in One-StTrEP-tag mouse line which allowing to analyze SHIP-1 molecule that constitutes key negative regulators of T cell activation.

By combining the study of this novel mouse model with the expertise in AP-MS present in the Bernard Malissen lab, I will generate the first unbiased representation of proteins (including surface receptors) interacting with SHIP-1 in T cells.

Protein complexes assembling around the selected “baits” will be isolated at four time points covering 15 minutes of pervanadate or immunoreceptor activation. The work described above is thus expected to yield a wealth of novel immune checkpoint receptors. I will validate such novel immune checkpoint receptors by CRISPR-Cas9 and provide mechanistic information on them.

Zeb1 regulates the development of NKT cells

Jiang ZHANG

Zeb1 is a TF involved in epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition. In the immune system, the role of Zeb1 is mostly unknown. A point-mutant mouse of Zeb1 (Cellophane mutant) has been shown that the NKT cell lineage was the most perturbed with a near-absence of NKT cells. Another point mutant mouse “Twirler” have serious neurologic problems and undocumented immune deficiencies and that has a mutation in a Myb binding domain in the Zeb1 regulatory region. This suggests that Myb and Zeb1 act in the same pathway to regulate NKT cell development. Both TF are expressed at low levels in NKT cells but high levels in their precursors (CD4+CD8+ thymocytes). Our working hypothesis is thus that Myb may regulate Zeb1 which is an important transcriptional factor of NKT cell development.

PRACTICAL INFORMATION

MEETING VENUE

220 rue du Château
F-67360 GOERSDORF
Tél. 0033 3 88 09 31 21
Mail. contact@liebfrauenberg.com
Web. www.liebfrauenberg.com

WIFI

Free wifi access to the internet: connect to the **PHENOMIN2017** network
No password required.

DAILY ORGANISATION

Breakfast: from 7:30 to 9:30
Lunch: 1:00 pm
Diner: 7:30 pm

LAST DAY / RETURN ON June 16th:

Bus leaves school location to Strasbourg train station at 2:00 pm.

ATTENDEES EMAILS

ALLEGRE	Nicolas	nicolas.allegre@udamail.fr
ARCUCCI	Silvia	silvia.arcucci@inserm.fr
BOUSCARY	Alexandra	alexandra.bouscary@gmail.com
COURREGES	Christina	christina.courreges@babraham.ac.uk
DERLE	Abhishek	derle.abhishek90@gmail.com
JUNG	Piotr	piotr.jung@babraham.ac.uk
KAMPYLI	Charis	c.kampyli@ucl.ac.uk
KELES	Erhan	erhan.keles@unibas.ch
KOBIALKA	Piotr	pkobialka@idibell.cat
KOKOCIŃSKA	Natasza	natasza.kokocinska@img.cas.cz
KOPPEROVÁ	Dana	dana.kopperova@img.cas.cz
KORSÓS	Gabriella	korsos.gabriella@univet.hu
KUČERA	Jan	jan.kucera@img.cas.cz
MACKINTOSH	Albert	mackintosh@fmp-berlin.de
MARTIN LORENZO	sandra	martinls@igbmc.fr
MUNIZ MORENO	Maria del Mar	munizmom@igbmc.fr
NATTARAYAN	Vasugi	nattarav@igbmc.fr
PARENTÉ	Alexis	alexis.parente@unilim.fr
PEREZ	Mattia	mattia.perez@etu.unistra.fr
RAMOS DELGADO	Carmen Fernanda	fernanda.ramos-delgado@inserm.fr
REBOLLO GÓMEZ	Elena	e.rebollo@ucl.ac.uk
SAMSÓ FERRÉ	Paula	sams@fmp-berlin.de
SANCHEZ-GUIXE	Monica	monica.sg7@gmail.com
SANJUAN RUIZ	Inmaculada	sanjuan-ruiz.inmaculada@etu.unistra.fr
TAO	Jia	tao.jia@inserm.fr
VORLOVA	Barbora	barbora.vorlova@uochb.cas.cz
WAEGAERT	Robin	robin.waegaert@etu.unistra.fr
ZANONCELLO	Jasmina	jasmina.zanoncello@gmail.com
ŽATEČKA	Václav	vaclav.zatecka@img.cas.cz
ZHAI	Yunhao	yunhaozhaicn@gmail.com
ZHANG	Jiang	jiang.zhang@inserm.fr

SPEAKERS AND ORGANIZERS EMAILS

AYADI	Abdel	ayadi@igbmc.fr
BEDU	Elodie	bedu@igbmc.fr
BIRLING	Marie-Christine	birlingm@igbmc.fr
DURAND	Estelle	estelle.durand@u-picardie.fr
FREMOND	Cécile	fremond@cncs-orleans.fr
GONCALVES	Isabelle	goncalve@igbmc.fr
HAGN	Michael	michael.hagn@helmholtz-muenchen.de
HERAULT	Yann	herault@igbmc.fr
JACOBS	Hugues	hugues@igbmc.fr
JONKERS	Jos	j.jonkers@nki.nl
LERONDEL	Stéphanie	lerondel@cncs-orleans.fr
MALISSEN	Bernard	bernardm@ciml.univ-mrs.fr
MALISSEN	Marie	malissen@ciml.univ-mrs.fr
MALLON	Ann-Marie	a.mallon@har.mrc.ac.uk
MEZIANE	Hamid	meziane@igbmc.fr
MONTAGUTELLI	Xavier	xavier.montagutelli@pasteur.fr
MONTOLIU	Lluís	montoliu@cnb.csic.es
PAVLOVIC	Guillaume	pavlovic@igbmc.fr
PENSAVALLE	Joëlle	pensaval@igbmc.fr
PIGUET	Françoise	piguet@igbmc.fr
POTTER	Paul	p.potter@har.mrc.ac.uk
REILLY	Patrick	reillyp@igbmc.fr
SCHMITT	Philippe	schmittp@igbmc.fr
SELLOUM	Mohammed	selloum@gbmc.fr
SORG	Tania	tsorg@gbmc.fr
TEBOUL	Lydia	l.teboul@har.mrc.ac.uk
VASSEUR	Laurent	vasseur@igbmc.fr
WENDLING	Olivia	olivia@gbmc.fr
WURST	Wolfgang	wurst@helmholtz-muenchen.de

Supported by

INFRAFRONTIER
mouse disease models

EC Horizon2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020
project grant agreement number 730879

Sponsors

Scan and discover!

<http://phenomin.fr>

contact@phenomin.fr

Annex 2

Good practices in the use of mouse model for biomedical research.

PROGRAM

This European continuing education course covered the following topics:

Monday May 20th: Mouse Genetics

Advanced mouse genetics programs: European and international new programs/ Basic overview of laboratory mouse genetics / Epigenetic/

11:00 AM	Bus leaves Strasbourg's train station to school location
12:00 PM - 1:00 PM	Welcome
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM - 2:30 PM	Introduction (Y. Héroult, PHENOMIN-ICS)
2:30 PM - 3:00 PM	Europeans Ressources: general overview (M.Selloum, PHENOMIN-ICS)
3:00 PM - 3:30 PM	Laboratory Mouse Genetics: basic overview (L. Montoliu, CNB-CSIC)
3:30 PM – 4:30 PM	Role of epigenetic in behavior studies (I. Mansuy, UZH)
4:30 PM - 5:00 PM	Break
5:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Workshop: group 1 - <u>12 participants</u> . Short presentation of scientific project and scientific issue/question/problematic

Tuesday May 21st Mutagenesis

Colony management and genetically drift / Mouse model generation and validation / CRISPR 9 genome editing in vivo / Mouse model for decipher the immunity / Mouse models for cancer research/ The genetic determinism of complex traits.

8:30 AM - 9:30 AM	Workshop: group 2 - 6 participants . Short presentation of scientific project and scientific issue/question/problematic
9:30 AM - 10:30 AM	Tips, Tools and Techniques to secure your mice projects and mouse colony management (A. Ayadi, PHENOMIN-ICS)
10:30 AM - 11:00 AM	Break
11:00 AM - 12:00 PM	Mouse model generation and validation, (M.C. Birling, PHENOMIN-ICS)
12:00 PM - 1:00 PM	Mutagenesis to decipher the mouse immune system, (B. Malissen, PHENOMIN-CIPHE)
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM- 3:00 PM	Mouse model for cancer research (J. Jonkers, NKI)
3:00 PM - 4:00 PM	The genetic determinism of complex traits and mouse models of human pathologies (X. Montagutelli, Pasteur)
4:30 PM - 5:00 PM	Break
5:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Workshop: "Choose and valid your model" + oral restitution of key emerging messages by the attendees

Wednesday May 23th Functional tests in mouse models / Advancing human health

Standardized exploration of physiological functions, scientific and ethical considerations, study design, analysis and data management, alternative imaging method tests / Preclinical approaches with mouse models, a first step toward the man, interest and limits

8:30 AM - 9:00 AM	Functional exploration, good practices, design to improve reproducibility of the data (T. Sorg , PHENOMIN-ICS)
9:00 AM - 9:30 AM	Experimental design and statistical analysis, (L.Vasseur, PHENOMIN-ICS)
9:30 AM - 10:00 AM	Imaging and pre-clinical applications, (S. Lerondel, PHENOMIN-TAAM)
10:00 AM - 10:30 AM	Break
10:30 AM - 11:00 AM	Behavior and sensory exploration: principle and case study (H. Meziane, PHENOMIN-ICS)
11:00 AM - 11:30 AM	Cardiovascular diseases exploration: principle and case study (G. Bouabout, PHENOMIN-ICS)
11:30 AM- 12:15 PM	Metabolic disorders exploration: principle and case study (J. Hager, Nestle institute of Health Sciences)
12:30 PM - 1:30 PM	Lunch
1:30 PM - 2:00 PM	Primary phenotyping of mouse embryo (O.Wendling, PHENOMIN-ICS)
2:00 PM - 2:30 PM	Interest of aging in modeling human disease, (T. Sorg, PHENOMIN-ICS)
2:30 PM - 3:00 PM	Crucial complementary aspects of functional analysis: anatomo pathology of the mouse (H. Jacobs, PHENOMIN-ICS)
3:00 PM - 4 :00 PM	Animal-based studies will be essential for precision medicine (J-L. Mandel, IGBMC)
4:00 PM - 4:30 PM	Break
4:30 PM - 6:30 PM	Workshop: "Phenotype your model" + oral restitution of key emerging messages by the attendees

Thursday May 23th: Animal Science & Environment / Ethics and welfare

Health, impact on functional studies, increasing safe / Mouse model diseases and bio confinement / Impact of the mouse gut microbiota / Good practice for good results/ Welfare assessment of genetically engineering mouse models

09:30 AM - 10:30 AM	Mouse model for human diseases and bio confinement (A. Zarubica, PHENOMIN-CIPHE)
10:30 AM - 11:00 AM	Break
11:00 AM - 11:30 AM	Microbiota and experimental mouse models of human disease (G. Pavlovic, PHENOMIN- ICS)
12:30 PM - 1:00 PM	The impact of maternal microbiota on the function of the newborn immune system (S. Ganal-Vonarburg, University of BERN)
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM - 3:00 PM	Round Table: Dirty mice and/or standardization? (H. Luche, A. Zarubica, PHENOMIN-CIPHE)
3:00 PM - 4:00 PM	Microbiota-host cross-talk in the juvenile growth and food allergy: lessons from gnotobiotic mouse models (M. Schwarzer, CAS)
4:00 PM - 4:30 PM	Immuno-phenotyping of mouse models in the Cytomics era (H. Luche, PHENOMIN-CIPHE)
4:30 PM - 5:00 PM	Welfare assessment of genetically engineered mouse models (I. Goncalves, PHENOMIN-ICS)
5:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Workshop: "Ethics and welfare assessment " - Practical illustrations

Friday May 24th: Data management / Resources / Animal research & society

Improving bioscience reporting and data robustness: ensure the reproducibility of pre-clinical studies/IMPC resource and data integration/Animal research and society/Day 5: Advanced programs in mouse phenogenomics, initiatives and resources

8:30 AM- 09:00 AM	Improving Bioscience Research Reporting (I. Goncalves, PHENOMIN-ICS)
9:00 AM- 10:30 AM	Using data from the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (L. Santos, MRC)
10:30 AM- 11:00 AM	Break
11:00 AM- 12:00 PM	Round table: animal research and Society (S. Wells, MRC)
12:00 PM - 01:00 PM	Round table: debrief, satisfaction survey, opened discussions on 3 selected major points.
1:00 PM - 2:00 PM	Lunch
2:00 PM	Bus leaves school location to Strasbourg's train station
4 :00 PM	Visit of PHENOMIN-ICS facility upon request (7 persons have already visited the platform)

Annex 3

European advanced school for mouse phenogenomics

2nd edition
June 12th - 16th 2017
Château du Liebfrauenberg,
Alsace, France

phenomin

Good practices regarding the use of mouse models for biomedical research

Supported by

PHENOMIN and INFRAFRONTIER

Germany, Spain,
Netherlands, UK

M. Hagn, J. Jonkers, L. Montoliu, L. Teboul,
W. Wurst, A.-M. Mallon,

France

X. Montagutelli, E. Durand

PHENOMIN's team

-B. Malissen, M. Malissen (**CIPHE**)

-A. Ayadi, M-C. Birling, E. Bedu, I. Goncalves, Y. Hérault,
H. Jacobs, H. Meziane, G. Pavlovic, P. Reilly, M. Selloum,
T. Sorg, L. Vasseur, O. Wendling (**ICS**)

-C. Frémond (**TAAM**)

31 participants / 8 countries

- 34 registrations and finally **31 participants**
- The audience consisted essentially of **PhDs and researchers**
 - 96 % answered their level was sufficient to adress this school : success of targeting the audience. 😊 (Only 3 researchers !)
- Participants came from **8 « European » countries**
 - 50% participant belongs to the ITN program IDIBELL (Spain) “Targeting the metabolism-immune system connections in Cancer”

Audiance

Nationalities

Lab's countries

Survey form: question and comments

87 % of the audience filled the survey

Assessment of the Advanced School in Mouse Phenogenomics : good practices regarding the use of mouse models for biomedical research

Thanks to circle the chosen answer.

To your opinion, the training program seemed :

Quite new
Standard
To need improvement

To address this school, your level was

Sufficient
Too high
Too low

The program has been respected

Precisely
Mostly
Hardly

Have you been satisfied by the balance between theory and practice?

Good balance
Too much theory
Too much practice

The program has been respected (92 %)

Precisely: 22 %
Mostly: 70 %

	Mutagenesis	Functional tests in mice models Experimental design	Animal science	Databases and resources Round table
Genetics	Mutagenesis	Advancing human health	Ethics and animal welfare ↓	
workgroup	Workgroup	Workgroup	Workshop	
		Social event		

Good balance : 15 %
Too much Theory: 85 %

Key points

- Less talks and more time to assimilate new concepts,
- more time for question and discussion with experts,
- move to more basic lectures to underline concepts than research topics analysis,
- more group discussion about animal work

Questions : key points

☐ The scientific program: 😊

- 48 % considered the content as innovative while 44 % considered the program as standard... (2 years ago, 71 % considered the program innovative with high scientific content)
- ✓ However, attendees requested less talk to have more time for assimilating new concepts (11% of the total number of survey)
- ✓ 44 % considered the duration adapted while 56% found it was too long (According to the program and their level)

- Did the school meet your expectation ?
 - 48 % « Absolutely », and 44 % « More or less »

- 100 % considered the school beneficial
 - 30 % considered the school to be « Very useful »
 - 67 % considered the school to be « Useful »

Questions : key points

□ Educational qualities of courses: 😊

- What do you think about the educational qualities of the speakers ?

85 % « Good », and 15 % « Unequal »

Proposed Improvements:

Sometimes too much triggered on research topic from the speaker, should move to more concepts; repeating concepts on different talks, sometimes overfilled with unnecessary information; move to basic lectures for crucial technologies/concepts to be sure that everybody have the same background over the school ; need more engaged discussion such as "brainstorming"

- The quality of teaching materials (equipment, documentation, resource, audio-visual...) 81 % « Good », and 19 % « Average »

They wanted table ! 😊 otherwise "it was excellent"

96 % would recommend PHENOMIN as a training provider ! (70 % « absolutely »)

Comment analysis :

Excellent 😊

- Overall very nice course
- Teaching materials and organization

2 remarks only ! And a lot of smileys at the end of the survey !
93 % found the atmosphere of the school friendly

To improve 😐

- Less talks and more time to assimilate new concepts
- Talks are too much triggered on research topics , should move to more concepts (academic form)
- Reduced time/part of the talks to assimilate the new concepts
- Move to basic talks in order everybody get the same background
- We need tables in the conference room !
- Poor internet connection /WIFI

Do not do it again 😞

- Bad food and vegan menu really worst-change location
- The speakers are not so good at all; one of them has just read its slides

Thanks to all of you !

EC Horizon2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020
project grant agreement number 730879

UNIVERSITÉ DE STRASBOURG

charles river

+++
ENVIGO

Survey Analysis and Statistics (2019)

Annex 4

phenomin

European advanced school for mouse phenogenomics

3rd edition
May 20th - 24th 2019
Château du Liebfrauenberg,
Alsace, France

INTERACTION WITH EXPERTS
METHODS SHARE OF KNOWLEDGE
SCIENTIFIC AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN
INNOVATION - ETHICS AND WELFARE

Methods and the good practices for the use of mouse models for scientific research

Program and application form :
<https://advanced-school.phenomin.eu>

PHENOMIN and INFRAFRONTIER

Switzerland, Spain

Netherlands, UK

S Ganal-Rondenbourg, J.Hager, J. Jonkers,
I. Mansuy, L. Montoliu, L. Santos, M.
Schwarzer, S. Wells

France

X. Montagutelli, JL Mandel,

PHENOMIN's team

-B. Malissen, H. Luche, A. Zarubica (**CIPHE**)

-A. Ayadi, MC. Birling, E. Bedu, G. BouAbout,
I. Goncalves, H. Jacobs, H. Meziane, G. Pavlovic, M. Selloum,
T. Sorg, L. Vasseur, O. Wendling (**ICS**)

-S. Lerondel (**TAAM**)

18 participants / 7 countries

- 21 registrations and finally **18 participants**
- The audience consisted essentially of **PhDs and researchers**
 - 10 PhDs, 5 researchers, 1 Engineer et 2 Master degree
 - 76 % answered their level was sufficient to adress this school : success of targeting the audience. 😊
- 37 % of the participants came for French laboratories. The others came from **6 other « European » countries**

- **12 nationalities were represented** (Spain, Slovakia, Italy, France, Pakistan, Lebanon, Ukraine, Poland, Germany, Bulgaria, China, Canada)

Survey form: question and comments

100 % of the audience filled the survey on line

Satisfaction survey 3rd PHENOMIN Mouse Phen ☆

European advanced scho

QUESTIONS RÉPONSES 17

Name

Réponse courte

Your Institute or Company

Réponse courte

Your global satisfaction *

1 2 3 4 5

Not satisfied Very Satisfied

To address this school, your level was: *

Sufficient

Too high

Too low

The program has been respected (92 %)

Precisely: 100 %

	workgroup	Functional tests in mice models	Animal science	Databases and resources
	Mutagenesis		Experimental design	Round table
Genetics	Mutagenesis	Advancing human health	Ethics and animal welfare	
	workgroup	Workgroup	↓ Workshop	
		Social event		

-Satisfied by the balance between theory and practice: 47 %
 -Too much Theory: 18 %

Key points

- Maybe special "questiontimes" can be included in the schedule where personal questions can be asked by participants to experts.
- Reserve more time for the workshops
- The advertisement didn't give me the impression of being advanced enough to participate. Maybe you can smoothen it a little in order to get more applicants.

☐ Global satisfaction : 😊

- 100 % are very satisfied

☐ The scientific program: 😊

- Did the school meet your expectation ?
100 % « Absolutely »
- 100 % considered the school beneficial
100 % considered the school to be « Very useful »

☐ Educational qualities of courses: 😊

- What do you think about the educational qualities of the speakers ?
100 % « Good »
- The quality of teaching materials (equipment, documentation, resource, audio-visual...) 100 % « Good »,

100 % would recommend PHENOMIN as a training provider !

Comment analysis :

Excellent 😊

100 % found the atmosphere of the school friendly and easy

- Overall very nice course (more time for statistics : 2 remarks)
- Teaching materials and organization
- Really nice atmosphere to ask question and exchange

To improve 😐

■ Description of the content/aim of the course

“The advertisement didn't give me the impression of being advanced enough to participate. Maybe you can smoothen it a little in order to get more applicants”.

■ Even more personalised support/help

- Maybe special "questiontimes" can be included in the schedule where personal questions can be asked by participants to experts.
- Maybe you could make groups of 3-5people (according to the PhD field), and each one assigned to speakers who would spend the whole week, that way they will be able to help us in a more direct way, which in my opinion was the only aspect lacking on the course - I have missed involvement from most of the speakers.

■ And more time for workshops

Do not do it again 😞

■ NO remarks !!!! 👍

Thanks to all of you !

JANVIER.
Rodent research models
& associated services
LABS

Université
de Strasbourg